

Vinyl Polymerisation by an Iron Complex

P. GNANASUNDARAM and H. KOTHANDARAMAN*

Department of Physical Chemistry, University of Madras, A. C. College Campus, Madras-600 025

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The kinetics of polymerisation of acrylamide, methacrylamide and methyl methacrylate initiated by dichloro bis(N-2,5 dihydroxy acetophenacylidene-*p*-dimethylamino anilino) ferrate(III) in DMF medium at $[H^+] = 8 \times 10^{-2} M$ was studied at $45 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The rate of polymerisation was followed gravimetrically and the chainlengths of the polymers were determined viscometrically. There was no polymerisation at $[H^+] < 4.2 \times 10^{-4} M$. The rate of polymerisation was found to be proportional to $[monomer]^{1.6}$ and $[initiator]^{0.5}$. In the case of methacrylamide and methyl methacrylate polymerisations, the initiator exponent was found to be 0.3. The apparent activation energies for the polymerisation reactions have been calculated. A kinetic reaction scheme is proposed on the basis of the experimental data.

STUDIES have been made about the catalytic behaviour of iron complexes towards polymerisation of vinyl monomers¹⁻⁶. Das and George⁵ studied the effect of iron(III) chloro complexes on the polymerisation of styrene. Dainton and Jones⁶ studied extensively the photopolymerisation of acrylonitrile initiated by iron(III) chloro complexes in DMF medium. In this paper, we present a systematic kinetic study of the polymerisation of acrylamide, methacrylamide and methyl methacrylate initiated by dichloro bis(N-2, 5 dihydroxyacetophenacylidene-*p*-dimethylamino anilino) ferrate (III) in DMF medium at $45 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Experimental

Acrylamide, methacrylamide and methyl methacrylate were purified by known procedure. N, N-Dimethyl formamide was allowed to stand over KOH pellets for an hour, then over CaSO₄ granules overnight before vacuum distillation. Perchloric acid (E. Merck, G.R., Ca 60% HClO₄) was used.

Dichloro bis(N-2, 5 dihydroxy acetophenacylidene-*p*-dimethylamino anilino) ferrate(III) was prepared according to the method of Singh and co-workers⁷ and its purity was checked by spectrophotometry.

The reaction vessel consisted of a Pyrex test tube (20 cm × 4 cm) fitted with an inlet and an outlet. A thermostated monomer solution, containing the calculated amount of HClO₄, was deaerated by bubbling oxygen-free nitrogen through the inlet tube for 30 minutes. After 30 minutes, the complex solution was added through the outlet tube which was then closed with a stopper. There was no induction period and the steady state rate was attained in about 15 minutes.

The viscometric average molecular weight of the polyacrylamide was calculated⁸ from the equation.

$$[\eta] = KM^\alpha$$

taking $K = 6.31 \times 10^{-5}$, where concentration is in gm/100 ml, η , the intrinsic viscosity, and $\alpha = 0.8$. The chainlengths (n) of the poly(methyl methacrylate) samples were determined using the equation given by Baxendale⁹, viz., $n = 2.81 \times 10^3 (\eta)^{1.32}$

Kinetic Scheme :

For the iron complex, the possible reactions involved in polymerisation can be represented as follows. The monomer formed an adduct with the iron complex which decomposed in the presence of acid to give the monomer radical, M[•].

where C was the complex and [M - C], the adduct. Such type of complex formation between the monomer and the complex was also proposed by Delzenne¹⁰ in explaining the second order dependence of the rate of polymerisation of acrylamide by aquopentammine cobalt(III). That the iron complex decomposed in presence of acid to gives Fe(II) species was supported by the disappearance of the absorption band at 20,000 cm⁻¹ and appearance of a new band at 28,000 cm⁻¹¹¹ (Fig. 1).

Propagation of polymerisation :

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of the Iron Complex $8.3 \times 10^{-4} M$ solution in DMF.

—, in the absence of acid.
 ---, in the presence of acid.

Termination of polymerisation :

Transfer reactions to the initiator leading to inactive products can also be considered

Termination by the primary radical, in this particular case is not different from termination by mutual combination. Since it is well known that many initiator systems form a complex with the monomer molecule, where the complex species functions as the initiator, the initiating radical is kinetically indistinguishable from the propagating radical. In orthodox systems like benzoylperoxide initiated system, the initiator decomposes in the initiation step to give a primary radical, viz., benzoyloxy radical which is different from the propagating radical viz., M_n^\bullet . In such cases, termination by primary radicals would lead to a rate expression independent of the initiator concentration. Assuming stationary state kinetics for M^\bullet and M_n^\bullet , and that termination by mutual combination takes place, the rate expression can be derived

to be

$$R_p = k_p \left[\frac{Kk_i}{k_{t_1}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} [H^+]^{\frac{1}{2}} [C]^{\frac{1}{2}} [M]^{3/2} \quad \dots (5)$$

Assuming termination by complex molecule, the rate expression would be

$$R_p = k_p \left[\frac{Kk_i}{k_{t_2}} \right] [H^+] [M]^2 \quad \dots (6)$$

If transfer reactions and mutual combinations are taking place, the rate expression would be

$$R_p = 2 \left[\frac{Kk_i}{k_{t_r}} \right] k_p [M]^2 [H^+] \quad \dots (7)$$

Results and Discussion

Free radical nature of the polymerisation is evident from the fact that polymerisation is inhibited by hydroquinone and retarded effectively by atmospheric oxygen.

The influence of monomer concentration on the rate of polymerisation was studied over a 10 fold concentration range in the case of acrylamide and a 7 fold concentration range in the case of methacrylamide and methyl methacrylate. The plot of R_p versus $[M]^{1.5}$ (Fig. 2) was a straight line passing through the origin indicating that the rate of polymerisation was 1.5 order in monomer concentration. This indicated the participation of the monomer in the initiation of polymerisation.

Fig. 2. Plot of rate of polymerisation versus monomer concentration at 45°C.

$$[\text{Complex}] = 4.768 \times 10^{-5} M \quad [\text{HClO}_4] = 8 \times 10^{-2} M$$

- A. Acrylamide ;
 B. Methacrylamide ;
 C. Methyl methacrylate

The rate of polymerisation was studied over a range of concentration of the complex viz., $1.193 \times 10^{-5} M$ to $1.193 \times 10^{-4} M$. The rate of polymerisation was found to increase with increase of initiator concentration. The initiator exponent was found to be 0.5 in the case of acrylamide and 0.3 in the case of methacrylamide and methyl methacrylate (Fig. 3). The deviation from 0.5 order in initiator concentration for methacrylamide and methyl methacrylate polymerisation indicated that simultaneous termination by mutual combination and by complex molecule was taking place. Similar variations of the initiator exponent with different monomers have been reported by a number of workers. Venkatarao and Santappa^{1,2} suggested termination by primary radicals in addition to the mutual combination to explain the deviation from half order dependence of the rate of polymerisation of methacrylamide photoinitiated by uranyl ions on the light intensity. Mitra *et al*^{1,3} in their study of polymerisation of methyl methacrylate initiated by cuprous ion in acidic aqueous solution attributed the low initiator exponent, viz., 0.38, to the mixed termination, i.e., termination by mutual combination and by primary radicals. Steric factors^{1,4} also had been advocated for such mixed terminations. If transfer reactions to the initiator were also taking place to an appreciable extent, the rate of polymerisation would be independent of initiator concentration (Eq. 7) which was not found to be the case.

Fig. 3. Plot of rate of polymerisation versus initiator concentration at 45°C.

- A. Acrylamide
 [Aam] = 0.6308 M [HClO₄] = 8×10^{-2} M
 B. Methacrylamide
 [Mam] = 0.7014 M [HClO₄] = 8×10^{-2} M
 C. Methyl methacrylate
 [MMA] = 0.9705 M [HClO₄] = 8×10^{-2} M

The rate of polymerisation of the monomers increase with increase of temperature. A plot of the logarithmic rate of polymerisation against the reciprocal of the absolute temperature (Fig. 4) in the range 30–50° gave 23.6 kJ mole⁻¹, 39.6 kJ mole⁻¹ and 54.5 kJ mole⁻¹ as the overall activation energy for acrylamide, methacrylamide and methyl methacrylate polymerisations respectively.

It was observed that polymerisation took place at $[\text{H}^+] = 4.2 \times 10^{-4} M$ while at $[\text{H}^+] < 4.2 \times 10^{-4} M$, there was no polymerisation at all. The rate of polymerisation was proportional to $[\text{H}^+]^{0.5}$ (Fig. 5).

Chainlengths :

On the basis of mutual termination, the kinetic chainlength which was a ratio of the rate of propagation and the rate of termination had been derived to be

$$n = \frac{k_p [M]^{\frac{1}{2}}}{(K k_t k_i \cdot \text{H}^+ \cdot \text{C})^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

The viscosities of the polymer samples prepared under various conditions of monomer concentration, complex concentration and acid concentration had been experimentally determined at 30 ± 0.1 . A logarithmic plot of the chainlengths versus monomer concentration and complex concentration

Fig. 4. Plot of rate of polymerisation versus temperature

- A. *Acrylamide*
[Aam]=0.6309 M; [Complex]=4.768 × 10⁻⁵ M;
[HClO₄]=8 × 10⁻³ M
- B. *Methacrylamide*
[Mam]=0.7014 M; [Complex]=4.768 × 10⁻⁵ M;
[HClO₄]=8 × 10⁻³ M
- C. *Methylmethacrylate*
[MMA]=0.3705 M; [Complex]=4.768 × 10⁻⁵ M;
[HClO₄]=8 × 10⁻³ M

Fig. 5. Plot of rate of polymerisation versus hydrogen ion concentration at 45°C.

- A. *Acrylamide*
[Aam]=0.6303 M [Complex]=4.768 × 10⁻⁵ M
- B. *Methacrylamide*
[Mam]=0.7014 M [Complex]=4.768 × 10⁻⁵ M
- C. *Methyl methacrylate*
[MMA]=0.3705 M [Complex]=4.768 × 10⁻⁵ M

had revealed the slopes to be 0.5 and -0.5 respectively (Fig. 6). Thus an additional confirmation for the kinetic scheme involving mutual combination had been obtained in addition to the direct evidence of the plots of the rates of polymerisation versus monomer concentration, complex concentration and the acid concentration. Thus all the kinetic data had been analysed by established procedures and equations, for proving the mutual combination reactions.

Fig. 6. Plot of chainlengths of polycrylamide and poly(methyl methacrylate) versus monomer concentration and initiator concentration.

- Polyacrylamide*
A; Plot of log n versus (1+log M)
B; Plot of log n versus (5+log I)
- Poly(methyl methacrylate)*
C; Plot of log n versus (1+log M)
D; Plot of log n versus (5+log I)

It will be worthwhile pointing to the unique nature of this iron complex as an initiator of vinyl polymerisation. The conditions of acidity are very crucial in this study. Polymerisation does not proceed below hydrogen ion concentrations of 4.2×10^{-4} M. Such a requirement has not been reported previously. In the photopolymerisation of acrylamide by potassium *tris* oxalato ferrate(III), the rate was observed to increase with perchloric acid concentration along with the molecular weight⁴. The kinetic dependence was not reported. In the present work, with increasing polymerisation rates, the molecular weights decreased. Diethyl (dipyridyl) iron(III) functioned as an efficient initiator for the polymerisation of acrylonitrile⁵. 40% conversion was reported in 5 minutes and no kinetic parameters were reported, though the authors stated that the initiator exponent was not 0.5. A co-ordinated anionic mechanism was proposed from spectroscopic evidence. Ferric dipivaloylmethide initiated polymerisation of styrene

and methylmethacrylate, exhibited a monomer exponent of 1.5 and an initiator exponent of 0.5 just similar to the present investigation^{1,5}. Initiation was proposed as due to the complex formed between the catalyst and the monomer, whereas in the present study, the decomposition of the iron complex proceeds independently of the monomer. The activation energy for the polymerisation of methylmethacrylate by ferric dipivaloylmethide complex was 27.2 K.cal.mole⁻¹ in comparison with the activation energy of 13.1 K.cal.mole⁻¹ for the initiator presently investigated.

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